

HRJust Method Memo A4

Elica Ghavidel Rostami, Stockholm University

WP5

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10455680

elica.ghavidel-rostami@juridicum.su.se

Executive Summary

The following memo shows examples of States use of human rights justifications (HRJust) within the mechanism of the Universal Periodic Review (UPR). The non-exhaustive list of examples has been collected from each of the included States' latest national report published on the webpage of the UN Human Rights Council with the purpose of illustrating how one can identify HRJust in the argumentation made by States. The system of reporting to the UPR is in itself already framed within a human rights context, which can have implications to the use of HRJust and other arguments. The important takeaways from the example study are:

1. Human rights are an integral part of States active political decision-making and depend on a range of different geopolitical/legal/historical/etc. points of departure, which is why different States have systematically different ways of using HRJust.
2. States use various different justifications in their arguments and decisions within the context of the UPR. In addition to clear examples of HRJust, States use HRJust mixed with other types of arguments, as well as arguments lacking HRJust altogether.

Example of HRJust: "Ukraine has introduced a procedure for "banning of international TV channels, movies and printed materials that endanger the independence, sovereignty or territorial integrity of Ukraine". [...] The State uses HRJust to justify the procedure and states that it is "justified under Art. 20 of the ICCPR and follows the requirements established in Art. 19.3 of the ICCPR"."¹

Example of HRJust + Development (Mixed): "Regarding the subject of Human Rights and the Environment, India uses HRJust mixed with arguments of development [...] and mentions that "the Supreme Court has interpreted the "right to life" to include the right to live in a healthy environment". Continuing on the subject, India reports that [...] the Paris Agreement was submitted on a 'best effort basis' keeping its developmental imperatives in mind."²

3. Future possible ways to analyse States use of HRJust within the UPR is to include the submitted Stakeholders communications, the recommendations from the previous review-cycles as well as the State's reporting's from previous cycles, in order to understand what States gain/lose by using HRJust.

¹ Extract from page 18 in the memo. More examples of clear HRJust can be found in the memo.

² Extract from page 12 in the memo. More examples of mixed arguments can be found in the memo.

Table of Content

HRJust Method Memo A4	1
<i>1. Introduction</i>	4
<i>2. China</i>	5
<i>3. Finland</i>	9
<i>4. India</i>	11
<i>5. Russian Federation</i>	13
<i>6. Sweden</i>	15
<i>7. Ukraine</i>	17
<i>8. The United States of America</i>	19

1. Introduction

This memorandum provides samples of States use of human rights justifications (HRJust) within the mechanism of the Universal Periodic Review (UPR). The memorandum is based on an example study of China, Finland, India, the Russian Federation, Sweden, Ukraine and the United States and their latest published reporting to the UN Human Rights Council Working Group of the UPR. The aim is to exemplify when States use HRJust, as well as other types of arguments, when reporting to the UPR.

2. China

In the latest national report submitted by China to the Human Rights Council (Working Group on the Universal Periodic Review, 31st session, 5-16 November 2018), the process and results of implementing the accepted recommendations of the previous review are presented.³ As a starting point to the report, China reflects on the concept and theoretical system of human rights and points out that there “is no universal road for the development of human rights” and that “the cause of human rights must be promoted on the basis of the national conditions and the needs of the people of that country” as part of the economic and social development of each country, seemingly using a mixed argumentation of HRJust, national interests and state sovereignty.⁴

The concept and theoretical system of human rights are then presented as “a road” of developing human rights with “Chinese characteristics”. This road, it is stated, takes national conditions as the foundation. The road is also explained to be a road that takes the people and their well-being and interests “as the starting point and end-result”. The report then goes on and explains:

“As it upholds the principle of the people’s sovereignty, China is developing socialist consultative democracy, perfecting the democratic system, enriching democratic forms and broadening democratic channels. As it upholds the principle of the people’s primacy, China is enhancing the people’s well-being and promoting the comprehensive development and common prosperity of the people as a whole. China has built the largest educational, social-security and grass-roots democratic electoral systems in the world, thereby affording unprecedented protections for the rights and interests of the people.”⁵ (HRJust)

China follows the HRJust cited above with argumentation drawing on development:

“This is a road that takes development as the priority. China has unswervingly implemented the concept of innovative, coordinated, green, open and shared development, steadily increasing its economic strength; its gross domestic product has increased from 54 trillion to 82.7 trillion yuan in the past five years.[...]”⁶ (Development)

³ In the national report submitted by China, reports by the Hong Kong Special Administrative Region and the Macao Special Administrative Region are presented separately. Examples of arguments used in these presentations have not been included in this memo.

⁴ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : China*, 20 August 2018, A/HRC/WG.6/31/CHN/1, p. 2, available at: G1825462.pdf (un.org) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

⁵ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : China*, 20 August 2018, A/HRC/WG.6/31/CHN/1, p. 3, available at: G1825462.pdf (un.org) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

⁶ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : China*, 20 August 2018, A/HRC/WG.6/31/CHN/1, p. 3, available at: G1825462.pdf (un.org) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

Following this, China describes that this road also takes the Rule of Law as criterion and the efforts of the Chinese government to bring about “scientific legislation, strict law enforcement, impartial adjudication, a law-abiding populace, and a law-based civil service”. At the same time, it is stated that “specific tasks involved in strengthening judicial safeguards for human rights have been clearly put forward and implemented in an orderly manner”.⁷ (HRJust + Rule of Law)

China goes on to propose a new type of international relationship featuring “mutual respect, fairness, justice and win-win cooperation”. China states that they “oppose human rights politicization and “double standards”” and advocates international human rights exchanges and cooperation on the basis of “equality and mutual respect”, attaching “increasing importance to the economic, social and cultural rights and the right to development that are of concern to developing countries, and promotes the comprehensive development of human rights of all kinds.”⁸ (HRJust + Development)

Leading up to the national legislative and institutional framework for the promotion and protection of human rights, China reports the following:

“[...]China has continuously improved and developed a socialist legal system with Chinese characteristics, comprising multiple legal departments of government, with the Constitution as its core and the law (including administrative regulations, local regulations and other normative documents) as its backbone, to be the foundation for safeguarding human rights and solidifying the rule of law. Citizens’ rights to subsistence and development, as well as their personal rights, property rights, basic political rights and freedoms, labour rights, education rights, social security rights and other rights have been effectively protected and guaranteed through legislation.”⁹ (Rule of Law + Development + HRJust)

In regards to the institutional safeguards for human rights, China states that it has drafted comprehensive plans for human rights development in accordance with the recommendations from the previous review. In order to promote the human rights in society as a whole, China states that they have compiled special explanatory reading material on the national human rights action plan.¹⁰ (HRJust)

⁷ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : China*, 20 August 2018, A/HRC/WG.6/31/CHN/1, p. 3, available at: G1825462.pdf (un.org) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

⁸ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : China*, 20 August 2018, A/HRC/WG.6/31/CHN/1, p. 3-4, available at: G1825462.pdf (un.org) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

⁹ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : China*, 20 August 2018, A/HRC/WG.6/31/CHN/1, p. 4, available at: G1825462.pdf (un.org) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

¹⁰ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : China*, 20 August 2018, A/HRC/WG.6/31/CHN/1, p. 5, available at: G1825462.pdf (un.org) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

Addressing the recommendations to strengthen judicial safeguards for human rights through reform, China gives examples of reform tasks led by the Supreme People’s Court and other reforms relating to for example procedural rules and reforms ensuring the independent and impartial exercise of procuratorial power in accordance with law. (HRJust)

Addressing the recommendations relating to the participation of non-governmental organizations (NGOs), academic institutions and the information media in protecting human rights, China highlights that 755,200 social organizations had been “duly registered in accordance with the law” and that regulations had been amended to promote and encourage the development of NGOs in the field of human rights protection. China also mentions that a new law has come to effect that provides legal protections for the rights and activities of overseas NGOs.¹¹ (HRJust)

Regarding the achievements and practices in the promotion and protection of economic, social and cultural rights and specifically the rights to subsistence and to development, China uses a mixed argumentation of HRJust and Development and mentions the following:

“In 2016, China issued the 13th Five-Year Plan for Economic and Social Development of the People’s Republic of China, which outlines a grand blueprint for economic and social development from 2016 to 2020. Concrete implementation of the 13th Five-Year Plan is playing, and will continue to play, an important role in guaranteeing the people’s economic, social and cultural rights and improving the living standards of the people.”¹² (HRJust + Development)

China addresses the relocation of poor people and argues that “in order to solve the problem of alleviating the poverty of the people in areas where the land they are living on cannot support them, the Chinese Government has implemented a project for poverty alleviation through relocation”. According to the report, 8.3 million registered poor people have been relocated between 2013 and 2017 in order to be given safe and practical housing, and in order to “escape poverty and take part in development”.¹³ (HRJust + Development)

Relating to Civil and Political Rights and specifically the issue of safeguarding the rights to life and to liberty of person, China references the Counter-Terrorism Law and uses a mixed argumentation of HRJust and National Security:

¹¹ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : China*, 20 August 2018, A/HRC/WG.6/31/CHN/1, p. 6, available at: G1825462.pdf (un.org) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

¹² UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : China*, 20 August 2018, A/HRC/WG.6/31/CHN/1, p. 7, available at: G1825462.pdf (un.org) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

¹³ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : China*, 20 August 2018, A/HRC/WG.6/31/CHN/1, p. 8, available at: G1825462.pdf (un.org) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

“In accordance with the law, the Chinese Government has handled cases of inciting and organizing acts of self-immolation, and the public security organs have cracked down hard on terrorist organizations and individuals, including “East Turkistan” forces, in accordance with the law, while at the same time ensuring that the human rights of criminal suspects are protected.”¹⁴ (HRJust + National Security)

¹⁴ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : China*, 20 August 2018, A/HRC/WG.6/31/CHN/1, p. 10, available at: G1825462.pdf (un.org) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

3. Finland

In the latest national report submitted to the Human Rights Council (Working Group on the Universal Periodic Review, 41st session, 7-18 November 2022), Finland uses HRJust in addressing the implementation of recommendations from the previous cycle and states that the Government has made “the fulfilment and promotion of human rights one the cornerstones of its programme” and that in order for Finland to continue to be “a safe and secure state governed by the rule of law, the Government must ensure that fundamental and human rights and legal protection are implemented equitably”. Finland states that they have adopted their third National Action Plan on Fundamental and Human Rights focusing on developing the monitoring of fundamental and human rights, with measures including “developing fundamental and human rights research and data collection, developing fundamental and human rights impact assessments, and enhancing the monitoring of recommendations from the Treaty Bodies”.¹⁵ (HRJust)

Highlighting the Government Report on Human Rights Policy, Finland uses HRJust to describe the Government’s policy on fundamental and human rights in international, European Union and national contexts and explains that Finland “defends the universal and legally binding nature of human rights and promotes fundamental and human rights, democracy and the rule of law”.¹⁶ (HRJust)

In regards to the pending recommendations on acceptance of international norms, the following is stated:

“The Government has not found any new reasons to change its view regarding the reservation to the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, the ratification of the International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families or the ratification of the Convention on the Non-Applicability of Statutory Limitations to War Crimes and Crimes against Humanity. For example, since Finland is a State Party the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court of 1 July 2002, the Government views that its article 29 covers *ratione materiae* the scope of application of the last Convention.” (HRJust)

Further along in the report, Finland addresses the subject of Persons with disabilities and states the following:

¹⁵ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted pursuant to Human Rights Council resolutions 5/1 and 16/21 : Finland*, 5 August 2022, A/HRC/WG.6/41/FIN/1, p. 2-3, available at: [G2244387.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

¹⁶ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted pursuant to Human Rights Council resolutions 5/1 and 16/21 : Finland*, 5 August 2022, A/HRC/WG.6/41/FIN/1, p. 3, available at: [G2244387.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

“Since the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities entered into force in Finland in June 2016, the National Disability Policy Programme (VAMPO) was replaced by a national action plan, which defines the national objectives for the implementation of the Convention, the concrete measures promoting the implementation, and the follow-up measures. [...] The Government acknowledges that further work is required – for example, there have been requests for a more systematic approach to assessing the impacts of measures on persons with disabilities. [...]”¹⁷ (HRJust)

Finland uses HRJust in addressing the subject of climate crisis, environmental degradation and the loss of biodiversity, stating the following:

“Climate change, biodiversity and environmental degradation are linked with many human rights, including the rights of indigenous peoples and children, enshrined in human rights conventions and treaties and with the fundamental rights guaranteed by the Constitution of Finland. Finland is taking action towards climate change mitigation and adaptation and to safeguard biodiversity so that fundamental and human rights can be fully realised. Finland emphasises this interconnectivity for example in its UN activities. Achieving the Sustainable Development Goals will also contribute to the realisation of fundamental and human rights in Finland and internationally.” (HRJust + Development)

In addressing the COVID-19 pandemic, Finland highlights that the pandemic has been “a test for the realisation of civil and political rights as well as economic, social and cultural rights” throughout the world and that it “has tested the Finnish fundamental rights system and the capacity of the rule of law”. Finland goes on to explain that managing the pandemic has “required restrictive measures that have interfered with people’s fundamental rights” but that restrictions “have managed to curb the pandemic and, consequently, protected people’s right to health and the right to life”. Reflecting on the measures taken to curb the pandemic, Finland states that “the measures to combat the pandemic have themselves had human rights implications” and that the assessment of actions taken will be important in order to address the long-lasting negative human rights effects.¹⁸ (HRJust)

¹⁷ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted pursuant to Human Rights Council resolutions 5/1 and 16/21 : Finland*, 5 August 2022, A/HRC/WG.6/41/FIN/1, p. 12, available at: [G2244387.pdf \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org/sites/un2.sites/default/files/2022/08/20220805_a-hrc-wg6-41-fin-1.pdf) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

¹⁸ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted pursuant to Human Rights Council resolutions 5/1 and 16/21 : Finland*, 5 August 2022, A/HRC/WG.6/41/FIN/1, p. 18, available at: [G2244387.pdf \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org/sites/un2.sites/default/files/2022/08/20220805_a-hrc-wg6-41-fin-1.pdf) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

4. India

The latest national report submitted by India to the Human Rights Council (Working Group on the Universal Periodic Review, 41st session, 7-18 November 2022) focuses on “the measures adopted, progress made and the challenges encountered in the country’s move towards realisation of human rights”. Addressing the subject of Equality and Non-Discrimination, India uses HRJust and states the following:

“Equality across varied social identities, economic conditions, political affiliations and cultural and other contexts is a hallmark of Indian democracy. Principles of equality and non-discrimination enshrined in the Constitution of India have been strengthened by various legislative, executive and judicial measures. The laws are fully and consistently enforced to provide adequate protections for members of religious minorities, Scheduled Castes (SCs), Scheduled Tribes (STs) and other vulnerable populations.”¹⁹ (HRJust)

In this regard, the work of the National Human Rights Commission (NHRC) is highlighted. The report states that the NHRC “continues to play a significant role in the promotion and protection of human rights in an inclusive manner” and that NHRC has established a Task Force for preparation of India’s National Plan of Action on Human Rights.²⁰ (HRJust)

India reports that it has been developing its business responsibility framework to “provide an enabling environment for improved participation of businesses in securing basic rights of the citizens”. Furthermore, India has aligned the National Voluntary Guidelines on Social, Economic and Environmental Responsibilities of Business with the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and has released a draft National Action Plan on Business and Human Rights for stakeholder consultations. Furthermore, it is stated that the legislative mandate of Corporate Social Responsibility “has enhanced the contribution of businesses towards securing human rights”.²¹ (HRJust)

¹⁹ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted pursuant to Human Rights Council resolutions 5/1 and 16/21 : India*, 17 August 2022, A/HRC/WG.6/41/IND/1, p. 3, available at: [G2246320.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

²⁰ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted pursuant to Human Rights Council resolutions 5/1 and 16/21 : India*, 17 August 2022, A/HRC/WG.6/41/IND/1, p. 3, available at: [G2246320.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

²¹ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted pursuant to Human Rights Council resolutions 5/1 and 16/21 : India*, 17 August 2022, A/HRC/WG.6/41/IND/1, p. 4, available at: [G2246320.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

Using arguments of development, India reports that it is “strongly committed towards holistic, equitable and sustainable development” and the National Development Agenda “echoes the 2030 Agenda and is in congruence with the right to development approach”.²² (Development)

Regarding the subject of Human Rights and the Environment, India uses HRJust mixed with arguments of development and highlights the commitment to “continue its efforts to improve the environment and address climate change” and mentions that “the Supreme Court has interpreted the “right to life” to include the right to live in a healthy environment”. Continuing on the subject, India reports that its Nationally Determined Contribution under the Paris Agreement was submitted on a ‘best effort basis’ keeping its developmental imperatives in mind.²³ (HRJust + Development)

Addressing the subject of torture and cruel, inhumane or degrading treatment, and the lack of ratification of the UN Convention Against Torture, the following is reported:

“India signed the Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment in October 1997 and remains committed to ratify the Convention. Since the subject falls under the Concurrent List, the Central Government shall also take into account the opinion of States in this regard. The Law Commission of India has been examining the changes required in domestic law prior to carrying out the ratification process. However, the existing legal framework, such as the provisions under the Constitution of India, Indian Penal Code, and Code of Criminal Procedure among others, guarantees adequate protection against any form of torture and cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment. In addition, Human Rights education is an integral part of the induction and in-service trainings imparted to police, security and judicial service personnel. National Human Rights Institutions also impart training to government officials on human rights in general as well as group rights.”²⁴ (HRJust)

²² UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted pursuant to Human Rights Council resolutions 5/1 and 16/21 : India*, 17 August 2022, A/HRC/WG.6/41/IND/1, p. 4, available at: [G2246320.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

²³ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted pursuant to Human Rights Council resolutions 5/1 and 16/21 : India*, 17 August 2022, A/HRC/WG.6/41/IND/1, p. 5-6, available at: [G2246320.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

²⁴ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted pursuant to Human Rights Council resolutions 5/1 and 16/21 : India*, 17 August 2022, A/HRC/WG.6/41/IND/1, p. 9, available at: [G2246320.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

5. Russian Federation

The latest national report submitted to the Human Rights Council (Working Group on the Universal Periodic Review, 44th session, 6-17 November 2023) by the Russian Federation (Russia) focuses on the results of the “work to further strengthen the regulatory and structural framework for the promotion and protection of human rights” and to implement the accepted recommendations.²⁵

In presenting the regulatory framework for the promotion and protection of human rights and fundamental freedoms, Russia uses HRJust and states the following:

“According to article 2 of the Constitution, human beings and their rights and freedoms are the supreme value. The recognition, observance and protection of human and civil rights and freedoms are the duty of the State. Chapter II of the Constitution is devoted to human and civil rights and freedoms and sets out a broad list of rights and freedoms subject to protection. The enumeration of fundamental rights and freedoms in the Constitution should not be interpreted as a negation or diminution of other universally recognized human and civil rights and freedoms. Fundamental human rights and freedoms are inalienable, are inherent in every person from birth and are directly applicable. Rights and freedoms shall be recognized and guaranteed in accordance with universally recognized rules and principles of international law and in accordance with the Constitution. In accordance with the Constitution, the universally recognized rules and principles of international law and the international treaties ratified by the Russian Federation form an integral part of its legal system. If an international treaty establishes rules that differ from those provided for by its laws, the rules of the international treaty prevail.”²⁶ (HRJust)

In the reporting of the legislative and institutional guarantees of human rights, Russia uses HRJust and explains that human rights “determine the purpose, content and application of laws and the activities of the legislature”. Following this, it is expressed that the “President of the Russian Federation is the guarantor” of human rights.²⁷ (HRJust)

According to the report, Russia has “legal arrangements for the non-application of the death penalty that are stricter than the international standard” and “sustainable guarantees have been formed of the human right not to be subjected to the death penalty”. Consequently, Russia argues that it is in

²⁵ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with Human Rights Council resolutions 5/1 and 16/21 : Russian Federation*, 24 August 2023, A/HRC/WG.6/44/RUS/1, p. 2, available at: [G2317208.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

²⁶ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with Human Rights Council resolutions 5/1 and 16/21 : Russian Federation*, 24 August 2023, A/HRC/WG.6/44/RUS/1, p. 2, available at: [G2317208.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

²⁷ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with Human Rights Council resolutions 5/1 and 16/21 : Russian Federation*, 24 August 2023, A/HRC/WG.6/44/RUS/1, p. 3, available at: [G2317208.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

compliance with the main provisions of the Second Optional Protocol to the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, although it has not acceded to that protocol.²⁸ (HRJust)

Regarding the administration of justice and the judicial system, Russia uses HRJust and explains that “the Russian Federation strictly follows international standards of administration of justice, striving to ensure the highest level of protection of human rights and freedoms”.²⁹ Further along in the report, it is stated that the Supreme Court “routinely brings information to the attention of judges and court staff on the international legal obligations of the Russian Federation, including those applicable to the protection of human rights and freedoms”.³⁰ (HRJust)

In regards to the subject of Prison and Law Enforcement Agencies, Russia uses HRJust and explains that it pays “close attention” to implementation of the UN Standard Minimum Rules for Non-custodial Measures. Russia continues on this subject and explains that alternative forms of punishment are used widely to reduce the number of persons held in correctional facilities, mentioning compulsory work and forced labour as examples of such measures.³¹

²⁸ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with Human Rights Council resolutions 5/1 and 16/21 : Russian Federation*, 24 August 2023, A/HRC/WG.6/44/RUS/1, p. 11, available at: [G2317208.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

²⁹ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with Human Rights Council resolutions 5/1 and 16/21 : Russian Federation*, 24 August 2023, A/HRC/WG.6/44/RUS/1, p. 13, available at: [G2317208.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

³⁰ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with Human Rights Council resolutions 5/1 and 16/21 : Russian Federation*, 24 August 2023, A/HRC/WG.6/44/RUS/1, p. 14, available at: [G2317208.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

³¹ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with Human Rights Council resolutions 5/1 and 16/21 : Russian Federation*, 24 August 2023, A/HRC/WG.6/44/RUS/1, p. 16, available at: [G2317208.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

6. Sweden

In the latest national report submitted to the Human Rights Council (Working Group on the Universal Periodic Review, 35th session, 20-31 January 2020), Sweden focuses on the accepted recommendations from the second cycle of the UPR process but some issues relating to the recommendations that had not been accepted by Sweden are also addressed.

The report addresses Sweden's national human rights strategy and states that the starting point of the strategy is the objective of ensuring full respect for the State's international human rights commitments. The national strategy states that a cohesive structure comprising of "strong legal and institutional protection of human rights, coordinated and systematic work on human rights in the public sector and strong support for work on human rights in civil society and in business" must be put in place to promote and protect human rights.³² (HRJust)

Sweden uses HRJust when addressing the incorporation of the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) into Swedish law. Sweden states that incorporation gives the CRC the status of Swedish national law and that this entails "a clearer obligation on courts and legal practitioners to consider the rights that follow from the CRC in deliberations and assessments" in their decision-making processes in cases and matters concerning children. Furthermore, it is articulated that "for the CRC to have an impact", it is necessary to continue the transformation of the provisions of the CRC into national law, alongside incorporation. Here, Sweden articulates the incorporation as giving a clearer responsibility for the courts, and at the same stating that transformation is needed for the Convention to have an impact.³³ (HRJust)

When it comes to the recommendations of ratification of Conventions that Sweden has not accepted, the State addresses these and argues in different ways to support their stand. In regards to the Third Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on a communications procedure, Sweden states that "if children are to be able to have their rights upheld, it is important that there are systems in place that enable them to assert them". Sweden continues on to state that "these rights can be asserted in different ways" and that the potential ratification of the Third Optional Protocol must be analyzed further before the Government can take standing on the issue.³⁴ (HRJust)

³² UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : Sweden*, 11 November 2019, A/HRC/WG.6/35/SWE/1, p. 3, available at: [G1932124.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

³³ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : Sweden*, 11 November 2019, A/HRC/WG.6/35/SWE/1, p. 4, available at: [G1932124.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

³⁴ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : Sweden*, 11 November 2019, A/HRC/WG.6/35/SWE/1, p. 4, available at: [G1932124.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

Regarding the recommendation to ratify the International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families, Sweden argues that the provisions of the Convention “are to a wide extent also regulated in legal acts of the EU” and that a discussion to potentially ratify the Convention therefore must be addressed at EU level. The State argues that this means that a unilateral approach “is not possible” and thereafter mentions that no other EU Member State has ratified the Convention. (HRJust + EU-/Division of Competences)

Further along in the report, specific areas of human rights are addressed. The first is “Rule of Law” and here the rights of detained and arrested persons are mentioned specifically. In the last paragraph of the section of Rule of Law, it is stated that “the UN’s Standard Minimum Rules for the treatment of Prisoners; Nelson Mandela Rules, and other international regulations” are used in the basic training of all employees within the Swedish Prison and Probation Service (SPPS). Furthermore, the international regulations mentioned are also held to be used as the basis of guidelines for the work instructions and internal rules of SPPS. These documents state how the SPPS is to conduct its work effectively, humanely and safely in line with applicable legislation and international commitments.³⁵ (HRJust)

³⁵ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : Sweden*, 11 November 2019, A/HRC/WG.6/35/SWE/1, p. 5, available at: [G1932124.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

7. Ukraine

In the latest national report submitted to the Human Rights Council (Working Group on the Universal Periodic Review, 28th session, 6-7 November 2017), Ukraine focuses on human rights developments in Ukraine as well as on the progress of the implementation of the recommendations received during the previous (second-cycle) review.

In the report, Ukraine uses HRJust in various ways. In presenting the key achievements relating to legislative improvements and institutional changes, it is reported that The Law on Principles of Prevention and Combating Discrimination in Ukraine has been amended to bring it “in line with international standards”. (HRJust)

Furthermore, the National Police has been re-established based on “the new principles of accountability, transparency, professionalism and respect for human rights”.³⁶ (HRJust)

In regards to the Human Rights Policy of Ukraine, the report addresses the Ukrainian National Strategy of Human Rights (NSHR) for the period of 2015–2020. According to the report, the Government has approved an Action Plan, which contains clear measures, indicators and deadlines to implement the NSHR. The report states that the preparation of the Action Plan had “an inclusive character” and was carried out with the involvement of civil society, international organizations, the Ombudsman and international experts in the field of human rights.³⁷ (HRJust)

Relating to the issue of human rights in the occupied territories of Crimea, Donetsk and Luhansk (Donbas), Ukraine states that the UN Human Rights Monitoring Mission in Ukraine (HRMMU) has been working in Ukraine at the invitation of the Government.³⁸ The report also states that Ukraine instituted the first of its five inter-State cases against Russia in the ECtHR concerning events in Crimea. Following the request of Ukraine, the ECtHR adopted interim measures, calling upon Russia and Ukraine to refrain from taking any measures which might bring about violations of the rights of the civilian population enshrined in the ECHR, notably under Articles 2 and 3. Other cases brought

³⁶ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : Ukraine*, 31 August 2017, A/HRC/WG.6/28/UKR/1, p. 3, available at: [1715166 \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org/ru/press/docs/2017/1715166.html) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

³⁷ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : Ukraine*, 31 August 2017, A/HRC/WG.6/28/UKR/1, p. 3, available at: [1715166 \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org/ru/press/docs/2017/1715166.html) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

³⁸ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : Ukraine*, 31 August 2017, A/HRC/WG.6/28/UKR/1, p. 4, available at: [1715166 \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org/ru/press/docs/2017/1715166.html) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

to the ECtHR concern violation of human rights in Donbas, further developments in Crimea, in particular the ban of Mejlis, the single representative body of Crimean Tatars.³⁹ (HRJust)

It is also reported that Ukraine, as a result of the Russian occupation, has adopted a Statement on Derogation from Certain Obligations under the ICCPR and ECHR. According to the report, Ukraine informed the UN Secretary-General that “Russia as an occupying power is fully responsible for the protection of human rights in the occupied Crimea and certain areas of Donbas”. Furthermore, Ukraine has declared its derogation from certain human rights obligations under the ICCPR and ECHR until “the cessation of Russian aggression and restoration of the constitutional order”.⁴⁰ (HRJust)

Furthermore, relating to the occupied territories, the report states that Ukraine “remains committed to its positive obligations to ensure to the fullest extent possible the preservation of human rights of people living in the TOT and Donbas”.⁴¹ (HRJust)

Regarding issues of Rule of Law and the execution of judgments of the ECtHR, the report states that Ukraine “attaches great importance to the jurisprudence of the ECtHR, which formulates and clarifies the European standards in the area of human rights” and stresses that the Government is committed to solving the systemic problems in Ukraine that have resulted in a significant number of applications to the ECtHR.⁴² (HRJust)

Regarding Civil and Political Rights and the freedom of mass media, it is reported that Ukraine has introduced a procedure for “banning of international TV channels, movies and printed materials that endanger the independence, sovereignty or territorial integrity of Ukraine”. The procedure also bans “the spread of war propaganda and the justification of the occupation of parts of Ukraine”. The State uses HRJust to justify the procedure and states that it is “justified under Art. 20 of the ICCPR and follows the requirements established in Art. 19.3 of the ICCPR”.⁴³ (HRJust)

³⁹ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : Ukraine*, 31 August 2017, A/HRC/WG.6/28/UKR/1, p. 5, available at: [1715166 \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org/ru/press/docs/2017/08/201708171001.html) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

⁴⁰ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : Ukraine*, 31 August 2017, A/HRC/WG.6/28/UKR/1, p. 5, available at: [1715166 \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org/ru/press/docs/2017/08/201708171001.html) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

⁴¹ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : Ukraine*, 31 August 2017, A/HRC/WG.6/28/UKR/1, p. 6, available at: [1715166 \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org/ru/press/docs/2017/08/201708171001.html) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

⁴² UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : Ukraine*, 31 August 2017, A/HRC/WG.6/28/UKR/1, p. 9, available at: [1715166 \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org/ru/press/docs/2017/08/201708171001.html) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

⁴³ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : Ukraine*, 31 August 2017, A/HRC/WG.6/28/UKR/1, p. 18, available at: [1715166 \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org/ru/press/docs/2017/08/201708171001.html) [last accessed 18 December 2023].

8. The United States of America

In its introduction to the national report submitted to the Human Rights Council (Working Group on the Universal Periodic Review, 36th session, 4-15 May 2020), the United States (US) Government states that its “commitment to human rights rests on a firm political and moral commitment to individual and corporate accountability and transparency”, seemingly drawing on a mix of moral and political justification. Continuing, the US states that “notwithstanding our political differences with the Human Rights Council and with the views and human rights records of some of its members, we welcome the opportunity to share the story of how our nation’s ongoing commitment to the protection of human rights works in practice”.⁴⁴

In explaining the methodology and consultation process of drafting the report, it is stressed that the responses in the national report “do not indicate that the United States necessarily regards the matters addressed as subject to U.S. international human rights obligations”.⁴⁵

When addressing the recommendations relating to the implementation of treaty obligations, the US states the following:

“[...] it is for each nation state to decide as an exercise of its sovereignty to assume treaty obligations which, once entered into, it has a legal obligation to fulfill. No state, organization, or tribunal, including the committees that monitor implementation of treaties, has any authority to impose, change, or expand through interpretation any treaty obligation to which the United States is a party.” (HRJust + State Sovereignty)

When addressing recommendations relating to Civil Rights and Non-discrimination – more specifically relating to racial profiling and excessive use of force by the police – the US rejects “that law enforcement in the United States is “systemically” racist” but do not “deny that more must be done to ensure fairness to all citizens, particularly members of the African American community”.⁴⁶ Further along in the report it is stated that “where there is misconduct by police officers or law

⁴⁴ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : United States of America*, 13 August 2020, A/HRC/WG.6/36/USA/1, p. 3, available at: [A/HRC/WG.6/36/USA/1 \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org/en/genref/doc/usa.htm) [accessed 18 December 2023].

⁴⁵ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : United States of America*, 13 August 2020, A/HRC/WG.6/36/USA/1, p. 4, available at: [A/HRC/WG.6/36/USA/1 \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org/en/genref/doc/usa.htm) [accessed 18 December 2023].

⁴⁶ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : United States of America*, 13 August 2020, A/HRC/WG.6/36/USA/1, p. 5, available at: [A/HRC/WG.6/36/USA/1 \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org/en/genref/doc/usa.htm) [accessed 18 December 2023].

enforcement agencies, state and federal laws provide effective remedies”.⁴⁷ The US do not use HRJust in its reasonings.

When addressing issues relating to Economic, Social and Cultural rights and the subject of Women and Health, the US is seemingly using a mix of argumentation of State Sovereignty and HRJust, but “in reverse”, as a form of justification for its arguments and decisions:

“As the United States has noted on many occasions, there is no international human right to abortion, whether under that name or under other terms like “sexual and reproductive health.” Rather, as President Trump has stated, “our Nation proudly and strongly reaffirms our commitment to protect the precious gift of life at every stage, from conception until natural death.” The United States believes in the sovereign right of nations to make their own laws to protect the unborn, and rejects any interpretation of international human rights to require any State to provide access to abortion. As President Trump has stated, “Every person – the born and the unborn, the poor, the downcast, the disabled, the infirm, and the elderly – has inherent value.”⁴⁸ (HRJust + State Sovereignty)

In regards to matters of National Security, a type of HRJust “in reverse” mixed with arguments of National Security is used when addressing the subject of migrants in detention:

“Recent years have seen a humanitarian and security crisis caused by a dramatic increase in the number of aliens encountered along or near the U.S. border with Mexico, including unaccompanied children. The majority come from Guatemala, Honduras, and El Salvador, where poor economic conditions and high levels of generalized violence, while not grounds for asylum or protection under the Convention against Torture or Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment or U.S. laws implementing it, are important “push factors. [...]”⁴⁹ (HRJust + National Security)

⁴⁷ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : United States of America*, 13 August 2020, A/HRC/WG.6/36/USA/1, p. 5, available at: [A/HRC/WG.6/36/USA/1 \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org/en/genref/doc/resolutions/A_HRC_WG.6_36_USA_1.pdf) [accessed 18 December 2023].

⁴⁸ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : United States of America*, 13 August 2020, A/HRC/WG.6/36/USA/1, p. 14, available at: [A/HRC/WG.6/36/USA/1 \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org/en/genref/doc/resolutions/A_HRC_WG.6_36_USA_1.pdf) [accessed 18 December 2023].

⁴⁹ UN Human Rights Council, *National report submitted in accordance with paragraph 5 of the annex to Human Rights Council resolution 16/21 : United States of America*, 13 August 2020, A/HRC/WG.6/36/USA/1, p. 15, available at: [A/HRC/WG.6/36/USA/1 \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org/en/genref/doc/resolutions/A_HRC_WG.6_36_USA_1.pdf) [accessed 18 December 2023].